

Short communication

CORYTHUCHA ARCUATA (HEMIPTERA: HETEROPTERA: TINGIDAE): A NEW ALIEN SPECIES IN MONTENEGRO

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Abstract

The oak lace bug *Corythucha arcuata* (Say, 1832), a species native to North America, is recorded for the first time in Montenegro. Specimens were observed in Podgorica in July 2025 on *Quercus robur*, where eggs and nymphs were found on the underside of leaves. This finding represents the last remaining country in the Balkan region where the species had not previously been documented.

KEYWORDS: oak lace bug, invasive species; first record, Montenegro.

Corythucha arcuata (Say, 1832) is originally from North America and has become an invasive pest in Europe over the past two decades. First recorded in Italy in 2000 (Bernardinelli & Zandigiaco, 2000), it quickly spread throughout Europe. This insect increasingly threatens native oak species (*Quercus* spp.) by feeding on their leaves, causing significant leaf damage and reducing tree vitality.

Material examined: Podgorica, Bulevar Svetog Petra Cetinjskog 2, Kraljev Park (42°26'17.8" N 19°15'49.68" E), 28.7.2025, groups of eggs and nymphs (larvae) on the underside of the leaves of the *Quercus robur*, K. Hradil observed and det.

New species for the fauna of Montenegro.

Oak lace bug (*C. arcuata*) was first detected on the Balkan Peninsula in the European part of Turkey (Tekirdağ Province) in 2011-2012 (Aysal & Kivan 2018, Çerçi *et al.* 2021). It was subsequently recorded in Bulgaria in 2012 (Dobrev *et al.* 2013), followed in 2013 by records from Croatia (Hrašovec *et al.* 2013) and Serbia (Pap *et al.* 2015). Further spread was documented in Romania in 2015 (Don *et al.* 2016), in Albania

(Csóka *et al.* 2020) and Slovenia (Jurc & Jurc 2017) in 2016, in Bosnia and Herzegovina in 2017 (Glavendekić & Vuković-Bojanović 2017, Dautbašić *et al.* 2018), in Greece in 2018 (Csóka *et al.* 2020), in North Macedonia in 2019 (Sotirovski *et al.* 2019), and in Kosovo in 2023 (Geci *et al.* 2024). *C. arcuata* is also distributed in other European countries, including Austria, the Czech Republic, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Moldova, Poland, Portugal, Russia (European part), Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine (Fig. 1), and in Asia: Iran, Georgia, Russia, and Turkey (Csóka *et al.* 2020, Gninenko *et al.* 2021, Hradil & Jégrová 2023).

C. arcuata lives mainly on oaks (*Quercus* spp., 27 species, host plants) but has also been found on many other plant species such as *Castanea sativa*, *Carpinus betulus*, *Corylus avellana*, *Crataegus* spp., and *Tilia* spp. (e.g. Csóka *et al.* 2020 and Kulinich *et al.* 2023). However, it is not certain whether the entire life cycle from egg to adult can occur on them or whether these were just accidental findings. It is possible that these plants may facilitate the survival of this invasive species, which has spread throughout the Balkan Peninsula in the last fifteen years. The finding of *C. arcuata* in Montenegro represents the species' first record in the last unreported country of southeastern Europe's Balkan region.

Figure 1. Present distribution map of oak lace bug *Corythucha arcuata* (Say, 1832) in Europe (red – European countries with recorded occurrence, orange – Balkan region with recorded occurrence)

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CORYTHUCHA ARCUATA (HEMIPTERA: HETEROPTERA: TINGIDAE): НОВА СТРАНА ВРСТА У ЦРНОЈ ГОРИ

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Извод

Хрстова мрежаста стеница *Corythucha arcuata* (Say, 1832), инвазивна врста пореклом из Северне Америке, по први пут је забележена у Црној Гори. Примерци су уочени у Подгорици у јулу 2025. године на храсту *Quercus robur*, где су на наличју листова пронађене јаја и нимфе. Овај налаз представља први запис за последњу преосталу државу на Балканском полуострву у којој ова врста до сада није била регистрована.

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